

Paper 14

A CRITICAL CASE STUDY ON QUALCOMM AS PIONEERS OF WIRELESS REVOLUTION

Sangeetha Prabhu¹, & Krishna Prasad K²

¹Research Scholar, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

²College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

E-mail: sangeethaprabhu96@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The company Qualcomm established in July 1985 by Irwin Jacobs and Seven at San Diego, California, the United States. Qualcomm is an American multinational company, it aims to design, develop semiconductors and market wireless telecommunications equipment's and services. Qualcomm derives most of its revenue from chip making and patent licensing businesses. Qualcomm has offices at almost 33 countries with a global workforce of approximately 35,400 employees. For the fiscal year 2018, Qualcomm reported annual revenue of US\$21.301 billion, an increase of 2% over the previous fiscal cycle. Its shares traded between \$51 and \$75 per share, and its market capitalization at the end of fiscal 2018 was valued at US\$105 billion. In the Fortune 500 list, the company ranks as 133rd in revenues among the largest US corporations. The company is focused on various industries like automotive, education, healthcare, networking, Internet of Everything, mobile computing, smart homes, smart cities, smart homes, and wearables. Qualcomm's products include Gobi, Hy-Fi, IPQ, IZat, Powerline, Snapdragon, Small Cells, VIVE, Wi-Fi platforms, Mirasol, Pixtronix, AllPlay, 2net, Brew, HealthyCircles, QChat, QLearn, RaptorQ, Vuforia, Halo, and WiPower. In this paper, we are analysing business strategies of Qualcomm by studying various things like the corporate history, financial strategy, STEEP and SWOT analysis, target markets, key company challenges and legal issues of Qualcomm.

Keywords: Qualcomm, Wireless Technology, Electronics Industry, Case Study, IT Company, Telecommunications Industry

1. INTRODUCTION

Today, there is a revolution in the world of communication and information transmission, which is wireless [1]. Wireless engineering allows you to communicate over distances between two or more people without cables and wires. This includes wave interactions with radio frequencies (RF) and infra-red (IR). The Internet affected the way people work, play and communicate. Shopping, research and message are all common uses of PC-based internet applications. In order to ensure cost-effective communications, the internet has rationalized business, personal and monitoring activities. The way people communicate also has an impact on mobile telephones. Cellular use has exploded since culture has been able to talk with each other everywhere at any time. Security and convenience issues are becoming significant motors in their increasing popularity. However, these two functions are combined in the next batch of cell phones. Consumers want to regulate their wireless phones via the

Internet. In all kinds of activities, companies want to be mobile. Therefore, companies will flourish that support and standardize the needed wireless equipment and technology. One such business is QUALCOMM. The basis for global Wireless Systems is the patented QUALCOMM Techniques. Their important research and development actions have enabled them to remain at the top of wireless technology, and a substantial income stream is provided by their wide patent foundation. However, QUALCOMM poses difficulties from multiple sides if it is to maintain its leadership position in the sector. These difficulties arise from other producers of chips, alternative wireless norms and telecommunication technologies sponsored by the government.

The QUALCOMM, Inc. dedicated to developing and supplying the multi-access code division (CDMA) electronic cable communications tools and digital technology centre. CDMA is a safe data transmission method for radio frequency. Qualcomm maintains a number of patents which are essential to its core business worldwide and promote various CDMA technological aspects. Prof. Irwin Jacobs & Andrew Viterbi established the business in 1985 [. Its aim is to create a ' Quality Communications ' company for the public sector, which is why it is called QUALCOMM. Qualcomm was built in 1985 with CDMA technology proposed in 1989 for the wireless industry. The present CDMA patents of Qualcomm are more than 400 US patents and more than 900 US patents. About 12 percent of the 550 million clients who use first-and second-century mobile technology use Qualcomm-based CDMA networks. Qualcomm's primary focus is on the global use of its 5th generation wireless model cdma2000. Qualcomm is divided into several branches including Qualcomm CDMA Technologies (QCT) and Qualcomm Wireless Systems (QWS), Qualcomm Technology Licence (QTL). Qualcomm Technology Licenses (QTL) provides producers with CDMA technology with charges and advantages. More than 90 telecommunications appliance manufacturers have been permitted by the company's portfolios of CDMA patents. The world's main manipulator for built-in circuits, systems software and tools for wireless device manufacturers and network equipment is Qualcomm CDMA Technologies(QCT). QCT now manufactures wireless platform circuits through its subsidiary, Snap Track. QCT generates revenue depending on CDMA from sales of products. Qualcomm Wireless Systems (QWS) provides portable communications and logistics leadership services and equipment for the transport sector with OmniTRACS solutions. QWS also creates and builds portals and equipment for the advanced satellite network Globalstar, which offers continuing mobile communication and data services.

2. AIMS AND OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

This is a company case study paper based on the information collected from Qualcomm's business strategies in wireless Technology industry sector. The paper deals with the following aim and objectives.

1. To learn the operation level and business level strategies of top multinational IT Company qualcomm.
2. To know the growth saga of qualcomm company.
3. To learn about qualcomm strategy of facing the challenges using their innovative slogan "forward thinking".
4. To know about QUALCOMM's strategies of exploring all possibilities as opportunities.

5. To use **STEEP and SWOT analysis** for the recommendation of Qualcomm's future strategies for accelerated success.

3. JOURNEY OF SUCCESS

- Qualcomm was established in 1985 in San Diego and is a leading worldwide wireless chip designer for 3 G, 4 G and 5 G devices.
- Qualcomm can now almost solely focus on its activity by resolving the licensing dispute with Apple.
- The 5 G generation is now under implementation, which means that profits and cash flows can be expected to increase in the foreseeable future.
- Qualcomm's valuation is favourable compared to the peer group and, despite the share prices rally owing to the Apple sale, is essentially undervalued.
- Moreover, a pending share buyback scheme of about \$7.8 billion and a current dividend of more than 3% also speaks in the future of an appealing shareholder value.

4. QUALCOMM'S INNOVATIVE SLOGAN: FORWARD THINKING

The slogan is a commemorative sentence, used for repeated expressions of concept or reasons in a tribe, politics, commerce, religion or other context to convince members of the audience or a more specified target group. The Qualcomm Wireless Reach™ project introduces sophisticated wireless systems to underserved societies around the globe with a view to enhancing financial and social development. The slogan or the business slogan of Qualcomm's publicity is "Forward Thinking". Mission statements and vision statements are written for corporate clients and employees. A Statement of a Mission may be described as a phrase or a brief paragraph published by a company or a corporation reflecting its key objective, identity and values and business principles. A sentence or brief paragraph is the definition of a Vision Statement which gives a wide aspirational future picture. Qualcomm Mission Statement is "Future Perspectives-We can see the future from the high heights of our dreams. Your vision of what may take place tomorrow inspires us every day. We aim every day to make this view the foundation of a new wireless world. So while nobody is sure what is going to be the future, we have a pretty good idea.

The old logo was a sad thing, with far too many inconsistencies to remove the "mm" ligature: the "Q" was too audacious, the "u" was too carved and condensed, and the "m" was the only rounded corner pieces. This new logo retains the essence of the old one— whose share of equity is strange and good— but rewrites it fairly perfectly. The space in each letter matches, the proper capitalization of the word is easier to read and the mm part of the wordmark is now far more integrated. It is still the only uppercase / uncase letters, but it is powerful and unified from the visual perspective. The "m" case and the redundancy were definitely explored but I like that they stuck with the transistor-esque-looking diagonal "ms." I'm sure that they stuck with the "m's". The subtle shading version of the rendering provides the logo a kind of interesting softness.

5. FINANCIALS

A comparative summary of Qualcomm's Financials for last four years 2015 to 2018 is given in table 1[3-9].

Table 1: Last four years Financial Statement

Revenue		30/9/2018	24/9/2017	25/9/2016	27/9/2015
Total Revenue		2,27,32,000	2,22,91,000	2,35,54,000	2,52,81,000
Cost of Revenue		9,795,000	93,55,000	93,15,000	10,1,06,000
Gross Profit		12,937,000	1,29,36,000	14,239,000	15,1,75,000
Operating Expenses					
Research Development		56,19,000	54,35,000	51,41,000	54,76,000
Selling General and Administrative		21,05,000	21,57,000	22,86,000	22,72,000
Non Recurring		-	-	-	-
Others		-18,000	-18,000	-18,000	-18,000
Total Operating Expenses		1,75,01,000	1,69,47,000	1,67,42,000	1,78,54,000
Operating Income or Loss		52,31,000	53,44,000	68,12,000	74,27,000
Income from Continuing Operations					
Total Other Income/Expenses Net		-47,18,000	-23,24,000	21,000	-9,40,000
Earnings Before Interest and Taxes		52,31,000	53,44,000	68,12,000	74,27,000
Interest Expense		-7,68,000	-4,94,000	-2,97,000	-1,04,000
Income Before Tax		5,13,000	30,20,000	68,33,000	64,87,000
Income Tax Expense		53,77,000	5,55,000	11,31,000	12,19,000
Minority Interest		-	-	-10,000	-7,000
Net Income From Continuing Ops		-48,64,000	24,65,000	57,02,000	52,68,000
Net Income					
Net Income		-48,64,000	24,66,000	57,05,000	52,71,000
Preferred Stock And Other Adjustments		-	-	-	-
Net Income Applicable To Common Shares		-48,64,000	24,66,000	57,05,000	52,71,000

6. SUSTAINABILITY THROUGH GREEN STRATEGY

Qualcomm is devoted to the sustainable use of wireless systems worldwide. Our strategy is sustainable by integrating financial, social and company governance issues into our business model, especially in relation to our key effect fields, such as the workers, supply chain and the local community. From their daily operations to their leadership and governance committee they have integrated sustainability across your business. Sustainability influences their strategic choices, their product design and their workers ' everyday thinking and behaviour.

The sustainable development task of Qualcomm:

- Develop technologies that transform the environment favorably
- operate at the greatest norms of ethics
- Be an excellent location for job
- Be excellent company individuals everywhere we operate
- Keep adding importance to stockholders

6.1 FRAMEWORK 'S PILLARS

The sustainability obligations of Qualcomm are in particular [3-9]:

1. Governance

- During all activities and relationships with their staking parties they show responsibility, honesty, transparency and ethical company methods.
- They are constantly improving their sustainable management, including better transparency, reporting, communications and measurable objectives.
- improve knowledge and exposure within their company and with contractual providers and main suppliers of human rights values..
- Review your corporate management values and procedures on a regular basis in order to guarantee that they serve the greatest interests of our stockholders and others.
- All employees are required to revise and recognize their Code, Foreign and corrupt laws and anti-corruption policies. They are also required to do so.

2. Chain of products and supplies

- They develop technologies to empower individuals around the globe and improve their quality of lives.
- They create products that take their economic and social effect into consideration.
- By applying and allowing accountable privacy and data security methods, they create confidence in the usage of wireless systems.
- They allow their semiconductor providers to behave in conformity with the Code of Conduct of the Coalition for Electronic Industry Citizenship and expect them to acquire products from environmental and socially responsible sources, including conflict free sources within and around the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC).

3. Workplace facilities and staff

- The goal is to boost diversity at all stages of the company and to continually develop and implement measures to tackle our talent pipeline gaps.
- They pledge to reward all their staff fairly and justly.
- They provide possibilities for all our staff for practice, development and promotion and encourage well-being, work / life equilibrium and general health for their staff.
- They are secure and healthy in their surroundings.
- It uses approaches to handle water use responsibly, to lower greenhouse gas emissions, to improve power effectiveness and the use of equipment, to decrease waste and to decrease hazardous substances throughout our activities.

4. Society

- They develop strategic connections with a wide variety of local organizations and programmes, which develop and strengthen communities around the world.
- Sustainable wireless initiatives, focusing on schooling, business growth, health care, the climate and public safety, enhance economic and social development and reinforce wireless technology.
- These programs promote needs in line with the development of Qualcomm and boost the volunteering of employees through creative programs with global local NGOs. They are committed to enhancing education in science, technology and engineering at all levels.

7. QUALCOMM BUSINESS TERATEGIES

You could just display a Qualcomm module on your desktop or on your mobile device. This is the major LTE chip maker and its products are available in nearly every mobile device brand. Only two of the biggest names with Qualcomm parts are Apple and Samsung. Its revenue is generated by the manufacturing and selling of these chips and the lending to other producers of the technology. In other words, comparing Qualcomm with a customer toll company's business model is simple. You are the only person in your business to do that, so you can put your own cost and get individuals to choose whether to pay. In the past 20 years, this business model has generated huge operating margins and incredible development.

Qualcomm is entitled to add its chips to 3 G and 4 G mobile devices in China with suppliers. The only issue is a continuing inquiry into the company structure of Qualcomm—the Chinese edition of the SEC, the NDRC. There is a matter of the quantity of lease charges and use privileges paid by the business. The inquiry resulted in some of the lower contracting organisations underreporting or failing the amount of units transferred for Qualcomm. The business has therefore changed its Wall Street selling figures. The ultimate domino in this adverse cascade is that shareholders have significantly reduced stock value. For Qualcomm there is also a prospective issue in China: the NDRC might start regulating its contract charges in China. China is the fastest increasing industry for intelligent devices and Qualcomm is the leading chip maker. Short-term income has already been impacted. The long-term prospects of Qualcomm in China might be influenced by its model of company.

The invention is a key component of the business model of Qualcomm: the Qualcomm business model shows some sustainability, in particular as far as research and development is concerned. It is not just profitability, it thinks. Qualcomm thinks it must be a goal of creation, for the creation is at the heart of human development. It could be asserted that this philosophy inspires a portable revolution. Qualcomm has created some wonderful stuff but has also motivated others to invent great stuff and use chips as their basis. "Inspire" is the keyword. The ultimate objective is to simplify and improve the connection of all parties. The business model of Qualcomm is as simple as feasible in some ways. They found a issue, solved it and continued to sell it.

8. SWOT and SWEET ANALYSIS :

it seeks at designing, developing semiconductors and business equipment and facilities for wireless telecommunication. The firm focuses on different sectors, including automotive, education, medical care, Internet of All, mobile computing, intelligent household, intelligent cities, intelligent housing, and wearables. Qualcomm is an American-based wireless company. It seeks at developing, developing semiconductors and marketing wireless equipment and facilities. It focuses on different sectors, such as manufacturing, training, healthcare, networking, the Everything Internet, mobile computing, intelligent homes, intelligent cities, intelligent homes, and wearables.

The SWOT analysis shows that[3-9]:

1. Strengths of QUALCOMM:

- In North America, CDMA is extremely invasive.
- Due to their violent security for intellectual estate, their capacity to safeguard patents is an significant competence.
- QUALCOMM offers funds to further expand research and advancement in order to deliver consistent revenues and profitability and growth.

2. Strengths of competitors:

- Cross licenses for new and competitive techniques, available free of royalties.
- The operational history and business existence have been created.
- More brand awareness.
- Longer access to the client base.
- Increased financial, sales, marketing, manufacturing, production and technology assets;

3. QUALCOMM's Weaknesses:

- The revenues of QUALCOMM are due to three Korean clients, losing 39 percent to any of QCT's significant clients. The revenues of Global Star accounted for 30% of the QWS segment revenues.
- A restricted proportion of third-party producers are dependent on the production and testing of goods. Any disruption to the operation of these third parties might damage service commitments, as described in Porter's five forces.
- QUALCOMM provides CDMA network financing to its licensees. If these customers do not recognize their debts, QUALCOMM's economic situation could be affected.
- Globalstar has elevated cost of facilities, which may adversely affect item development

4. Weaknesses of rivals:

- Competitors ' network technology focuses mainly on GSM. If they do not have new technology to meet 3 G networks, their development can be limited.
- Competition in North America has a restricted business share.
-

5. QUALCOMM's Opportunities:

- Opportunities for QUALCOMM:• Third generation wireless communication requires of the sector.

- Emerging economies in Asia, especially China and India. The total population of both these economies is about 2.2 billion or 40% of the world's inhabitants.
- Spinco will contribute to all-embracing its permits.
- CDMA is expected to contribute to significant development in revenues.

6. Competitors' Opportunities:

- Wireless communication needs of the industry for third generation.
- Asian emerging markets, China and India in particular. Both of these markets have a combined population of about 2.2 billion or 40% of the world's population.
- Open the door to new products can be adopted for alternative standards..

7. Common threats both for and against the QUALCOMM:

- Rapid changes in technology could make current goods outdated.
- A deterioration of the execution of a fresh item could affect business share and income.
- Poor economic health will have a negative impact on significant clients' profitability.
- International overseas exchange instability and fluctuation can hamper development and revenues.
- The acceptance of network technology of third generation.
- Health hazards. In the medical sector, several White Papers debating whether wireless emissions can be associated with various health problems, such as cancer, have been released. This may discourage the consumers of this item, which affects the sale of licenses for technology.

The assessment by STEEP shows[3-9]:

1. **Situation:** Wireless interaction and robotics are the early phase of the product life cycle. During the next century, many fresh technology types could be developed and fresh companies and partnerships could be formed. Satellite communications are developing and can provide a feasible solution to land-based wireless systems.
2. **Technology:** At the beginning of the design phase. New technology is developing quickly and the mental benefit to QUALCOMM is to achieve its economic goals.
3. **Economic:** The scenario is unsure at the moment. In the financial year 2000, QUALCOMM relies on 47% of its global clients. In an abrupt foreign economy, its revenue and earnings are being adjusted. In addition, their income is adversely impacted when customer expenditure continues to stagnate in the US.
4. **Political:** As mentioned, if the policy environment shifts in Korea or China, the effects of QUALCOMM are also immediate and 47% of revenues depend on global customers.

9. CONCLUSION

The document addressed the company's business policies, finance, business policies and pillars to reach its goals. Qualcomm IT Company. The benefits and benefits of these corporate procedures and policies used to distinguish their efficiency within the organization are also examined. Wireless conversion technology and license patent facilities are provided by Qualcomm. Detailed data on business strategies of Qualcomm was given and how these policies had an impact on the company's growth.

REFERENCES

- [1] Bhushan, N., Li, J., Malladi, D., Gilmore, R., Brenner, D., Damnjanovic, A., ... & Geirhofer, S. (2014). Network densification: the dominant theme for wireless evolution into 5G. *IEEE Communications Magazine*, 52(2), 82-89.
- [2] Levin, M. S. (2017). Towards combinatorial modeling of wireless technology generations. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1708.08996*.
- [3] Dr. Irwin Mark Jacobs, & Richard SULPIZIO (1999). Big ideas enabled by CDMA Retrieved from http://www.annualreports.com/HostedData/AnnualReportArchive/q/NASDAQ_QCOM_1999.pdf
- [4] Steve Mollenkopf (2016). QUALCOMM Incorporated Annual report 2016 Retrieved from http://www.annualreports.com/HostedData/AnnualReportArchive/q/NASDAQ_QCOM_2016.pdf
- [5] George S. Davis (2017). QUALCOMM INC/DE Annual report 2017 Retrieved from http://www.annualreports.com/HostedData/AnnualReportArchive/q/NASDAQ_QCOM_2017.pdf
- [6] George S. Davis (2015). QUALCOMM INC/DE Annual report 2015 Retrieved from http://www.annualreports.com/HostedData/AnnualReportArchive/q/NASDAQ_QCOM_2015.pdf
- [7] George S. Davis (2014). QUALCOMM INC/DE Annual report 2014 Retrieved from http://www.annualreports.com/HostedData/AnnualReportArchive/q/NASDAQ_QCOM_2014.pdf
- [8] George S. Davis (2013). QUALCOMM INC/DE Annual report 2013 Retrieved from http://www.annualreports.com/HostedData/AnnualReportArchive/q/NASDAQ_QCOM_2013.pdf
- [9] William F. Davidson, Jr. (2005). QUALCOMM Annual report 2005 Retrieved from http://www.annualreports.com/HostedData/AnnualReportArchive/q/NASDAQ_QCOM_2005.pdf
- [10]
- [11] K. A. Grajski and E. Kirk, "Towards a Mobile Multimedia Age – Location-Based Services: A Case Study," *Wirel. Pers. Commun.*, vol. 26, no. 2, pp. 105–116, Sep. 2003.
- [12] P. Bender, P. Black, M. Grob, R. Padovani, N. Sindhushayana, and A. Viterbi, "CDMA/HDR: A Bandwidth-Efficient High-Speed Wireless Data Service for Nomadic Users," in *The Foundations of the Digital Wireless World*, vol. Volume 2, 0 vols., Co-Published with Indian Institute of Science (IISc), Bangalore, India, 2009, pp. 161–168.
- [13] N. Gandal, D. Salant, and L. Waverman, "Standards in wireless telephone networks," *Telecommun. Policy*, vol. 27, no. 5, pp. 325–332, Jun. 2003.
- [14] L. Kimmel, "Broadcom's Proposed Acquisition of Qualcomm: A Bad Deal for Innovation and Consumers," *SSRN Electron. J.*, 2018.
- [15] D. B. Yoffie and A. S. Choi, "Qualcomm Inc., 2019," Jun. 2018.
- [16] L. Hou, "Qualcomm: How China has Invalidated Traditional Business Models on Standard Essential Patents," *J. Eur. Compet. Law Pract.*, vol. 7, no. 10, pp. 686–689, Dec. 2016.

- [17] D. H. Ginsburg, J. D. Wright, and L. Edwards, “Section 2 Mangled: FTC v. Qualcomm on the Duty to Deal, Price Squeezes, and Exclusive Dealing,” SSRN Electron. J., 2019.
- [18] M. J. Adeleke, A. Grebe, M. Kretschmer, and J. Moedeke, “Spectrum Utilization Assessment of Wi-Fi Network Using Qualcomm/Atheros 802.11 Wireless Chipset,” in e-Infrastructure and e-Services for Developing Countries, 2018, pp. 180–191.
- [19] J. Gum and C. Patrick, “System and method for integration of wireless computer network in position determining technology,” US7647055B2, 12-Jan-2010.
- [20] Dulababu, T. (2017). Case Study: A Diagnostic Study on Fundamentals of Top Indian IT Companies. *Advances in Management*, 10(3), 8-20.
- [21] Maria Bonaventura Forleo & Nadia Palmieri (2019) The potential for developing educational farms: a SWOT analysis from a case study, *The Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension*, DOI: 10.1080/1389224X.2019.1643747 Francisco Javier Forcadell, Elisa Aracil and
- [22] Fernando Úbeda, The Influence of Innovation on Corporate Sustainability in the International Banking Industry, *Sustainability*, 10.3390/su11113210, 11, 11, (3210), (2019).